

TEACHER ACTIVITY IN INNOVATIVE ANALYSIS OF ARTISTIC TEXTS IN PRIMARY EDUCATION

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Abstract: In this article, the scientific-theoretical basis of the development of innovative activities of teachers in the analysis of artistic texts in primary classes in the modern education system is analyzed.

Key words: Activity, scientific research, creation of developments, experience - testing, preparation, planning, implementation, advanced pedagogical technologies, interactive methods, etc.

In the process of renewal of world pedagogy, it is necessary to improve the ability of teachers to seek new things, to independently search for new things, to create and use them, to improve the skills of conducting lessons and extracurricular activities using advanced pedagogical technologies and interactive methods.

Innovative activity is the creation of scientific research, development, experiment-testing, or the creation of a new technological process or a new product under new improved conditions using other scientific and technical achievements. The original content of innovative activity is the formation of a new technology in practice, the result of which is the activity aimed at turning the invention into a project, the project into a technology.

Innovative activity arises from the teacher's dissatisfaction with his work. It arises on the basis of the teacher's desire to successfully solve this or that pedagogical task when he encounters an obstacle. Innovative activity begins with the search for a new idea.

Pedagogical innovation requires a new approach to the educational process and its management from the teacher due to the fact that it is directed to the solution of an important and complex problem in the educational process.

There are different approaches to analyzing the structure of the teacher's innovative activity. For example, according to A. Nikolskaya, activity renewal takes place in 3 stages:

- preparation;
- planning;

- consists of implementation.

There are a number of psychological obstacles in preparing teachers for innovative activities. The first of these is that it is very difficult for the teacher to go beyond the limits of the activities he is used to, that is, there is insufficient creativity in teachers, and another reason is that new and unknown things always scare people and is to cause danger.

A.M. Khan distinguishes two types of psychological barriers encountered by teachers in the formation of innovative activities: cognitive psychological barriers and barriers that appear regularly. Cognitive psychological barriers are lack of knowledge about innovation, dislike of innovation and passive actions, while regular psychological barriers are manifested in the form of lack of trust in innovation, lack of trust in management, lack of support for initiatives and usually fighting against innovators. .

As the demands of the times change rapidly, the field of education changes with it and requires the teacher to change his activities. Today, the main task of a teacher is not only to teach, but also to manage, and he is required to organize and manage the educational process based on innovations.

Innovative activity is the main activity that determines the success of a teacher, and it means the qualitative reconstruction of his personal, professional, pedagogical and methodical skills.

It is appropriate to analyze the teacher's readiness for innovative activities in 3 stages:

1. Analysis of the activity of the innovation before its use in pedagogical activities;
2. Analysis of the period of active formation of innovative activity;
3. Analysis of the activity in the period after the introduction of innovation to the pedagogical process.

It is known that the characteristics and qualities of a person are formed in the process of pedagogical activity and are the result of his activity. For this reason, it is necessary to inculcate in teachers the psychology of always feeling the need for innovation and constant independent study. Because novelty gives a person more pleasure than grandeur.

Nowadays, updating the teacher's pedagogical activities and introducing innovations into the educational process are considered to be one of the main tasks that cannot be delayed. Especially in this field, it is determined by the level of professional

training of teachers, knowledge, skills, qualifications, creative potential, and professional skills that are reflected in their non-standard thinking.

Organization of the teacher's innovative activity, the stages of its formation can be defined as follows:

Stage 1 - prepared methodical recommendations are clearly copied and applied.

2nd stage - some new devices (modifications) and methods are introduced into the existing system.

3rd stage - the content, methods and form of implementation of the new idea are fully developed.

4 - stage - the teacher develops his own concept and methodology of teaching and upbringing.

The main driving force in preparing a teacher for innovative activities is the psychological environment in the pedagogical team, the extent to which the team members are aware of the news in the world education market. Many scientists emphasize that the creative environment in the pedagogical team has a special role in the formation of the innovative activity of the teacher. Based on innovative characteristics of teachers and their positive attitude to innovations in the educational process, K. Rogers and K. Angelovsky suggest dividing the members of the pedagogical team into 5 groups.

1. Innovators
2. Previous executors
3. The previous majority
4. The next majority
5. Hesitating

Improving the quality of education leads to the improvement of life and prosperity in all aspects of society. Since the introduction of innovation is an effective means of improving the quality of education, developed countries try to continuously introduce innovation into the educational process.

The experience of many developed countries shows that active participation of all links in the educational system is demonstrated in innovative processes. Therefore, in our country, scientific and research work is being carried out on the problems of developing pedagogical innovations. Among them, pedagogic scientists N. Azizkhojaeva, B. Farbermon, N. Saydiahmedov, M. Ochilov, M. Jumaniyozova and others can be cited.

But the experience of many countries shows that if the innovation process moves from top to bottom, and the teacher becomes a subordinate executor, that is, only a consumer of innovation, then this process takes on a bureaucratic tone.

In conclusion, it can be said that the quality and efficiency can be guaranteed only if the teacher is ready for innovative activities, brings the latest innovations to the lesson, organizes it in an interesting way for the student and in accordance with his needs.

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